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Open access publishing in and beyond the Global North

– Elie Gore

Publishing academic books open access can make research available to a truly global audience.

Academics in the Global South are structurally disadvantaged compared to academics in the Global North. Paywalls, the cost of academic books, and other barriers to accessing resources exacerbate longstanding material and epistemological inequalities between institutions and academics in the Global North and those in the Global South.

Queer politics and activism in Ghana

Dr Ellie Gore, Lecturer in Global Political Economy in the Department of Politics, University of Manchester, has written their first open access book. Entitled *Between HIV Prevention and LGBTI Rights: The Political Economy of Queer Activism in Ghana*, the book is based on ethnographic research conducted with LGBTI/HIV activists and organisations in Ghana. It's an emerging area of academic research and Gore says it was important that the book was made available to as wide an audience as possible, both to have maximum impact and for ethical reasons.

They added:

“I’m hoping it’s not just academics and researchers that read it. I’d like to think it is of interest to policymakers, activists, civil society organisations in Africa and around

the world who are concerned about LGBTI rights and the struggle for queer liberation.”

A Ghanaian audience

Above all, Gore wants their research to be available to their colleagues and other stakeholders in Ghana, including everyone who participated in the fieldwork. Had they not gone open access, it would have been difficult for most people in Ghana to access the book.

Gore says this has happened time and time again. They explained:

“ Research conducted in parts of the Global South, and in Africa in particular, can be very extractive. Academics from the Global North go there, get their data, then write their publications – and who gets to read them? This is one small way of trying to mitigate that extractive dynamic.

Who produces knowledge about Africa?

Gore thinks that a lot more needs to be done to ensure that academics, activists, and other voices from across Africa can push back against the discourses and narratives created by the Global North about the continent. Indeed, as a British academic, Gore wasn't sure if they should write their book at all. Ultimately, they hoped that by publishing their findings and putting the voices and experiences of queer Ghanaian activists centre stage, the book might make a small but valuable contribution to understanding queer politics in West Africa.

Gore's experience of publishing open access

As an academic based at the University of Manchester, publishing open access was easier than Gore had expected.

They said:

“I had thought it might be difficult to publish open access, but it turned out there were a few possible routes available to me.”

The University of Manchester runs an Open Access monograph competition, whereby the university's library pays the publishing costs, so that was one potential route. The other option was the UKRI's longform open access central fund. As

Gore's research was funded by an ERSC doctoral scholarship and an ESRC postdoctoral fellowship, they went for the latter option.

Open access – good and bad

While Gore thinks that open access can help address issues in who has access to knowledge, they are concerned about ongoing inequalities in who can publish their research and therefore whose knowledge and contribution is privileged and valued. African and Ghanaian ways of knowing are still often marginalised at best, if not excluded altogether.

They explained:

“If you are a Ghanaian academic working in a Ghanaian university, you are unlikely to have the resources or means to publish something open access.”

Gore says there needs to be a more radical and transformative approach to tackling the extractive logics and unequal power relations built into current academic research and publishing models.